

CLASSIFICATION OF PRODUCT QUALITY INDICATORS.**ABDURAZOQOVA BAXRINISO GAYRAT QIZI***Jizzakh Polytechnic institute, student,**Phone number: +998931373102; abdurazzoqovabaxriniso@gmail.com***BADALOV NOMOZ JURABOYEVICH***Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, associate professor,**Phone number: +998903110662; nomozbadalov@gmail.com**Orcid: 0000-0003-3392-9150*

Abstract: According to the number of properties that describe the set of quality indicators of the product, various properties of the product, the stages of determination, the method of determination, the nature of use for evaluating the quality level, the method of expression and can be classified according to their characteristics.

Keywords: product, quality, standard, competition, system, standardization, metrology, quality system, regulatory document, quality management, regulation, quality indicators.

In assessing the technical level and quality of the product, the indicators of conformity of the quality indicators to the intended task, which describe the effectiveness of the use and use of the product and determine the field of its application, indicators of its reliability and long-term durability when using the product under certain conditions [1], design and technological solutions to ensure high labor productivity in the manufacture and repair of products technological indicators of product preparation describing the efficiency, standardization and unification indicators describing the level of use of standardized items in the product and the level of unification of product components, hygienic , mental , taking into account the set of anthropometric, physiological, psychophysiological characteristics, ergonomic indicators, product attractiveness, impressiveness, originality, harmony, aesthetic indicators describing properties such as elegance,

environment and style [2], patent-legal indicators describing the level of patent protection of the product in the country and abroad, as well as its patent purity, reflecting the costs of product development, preparation and use (consumption), as well as the economic efficiency of its use groups of economic indicators are used. At present, in addition to the traditional group of indicators listed above, ecological indicators, indicators of product safety and transportability, and indicators of homogeneity of the structure are used in the evaluation of the technical level and quality of the product [3]. Effective management also involves the use of general indicators, which describe the quality of the manufactured product, regardless of its type and intended purpose [4]. Among them, in particular, the total volume of production of products belonging to a certain group, the volume and weight of the production of some types of advanced, high-performance products, the economic effect of using products of higher quality, and the indicators of variety for the products of several industries can be included. Summarizing indicators of quality are used in the plans of enterprises, research and design, and construction organizations [5]. Based on the level of these indicators, it is possible to think about the quality of the product produced in the entire enterprise or network [6]. Indicators of compatibility of the product with the specified task, indicators of compatibility of the product with the specified task describe the properties that determine the main tasks that the product is intended to perform and determine its field of application [7]. Indicators of compatibility of the product with the specified task functional and technical efficiency, structural composition, and structure are divided into indicators [8]. Indicators of conformity of the product to the intended function belong to the group of indicators of use, and indicators of use, in turn, belong to the group of technical indicators of product quality. Functionality indicators describe the degree of conformity of the product to its intended purpose, structural execution and main dimensions, and resistance to external influences and loads. Indicators of conformity of the product to its intended function are inextricably linked with other indicators that determine its quality. If the required values of the interrelated indicators of

quality are not provided, it will be very difficult for the product to perform its task effectively [9]. When choosing the nomenclature of indicators of compliance of the product for quality assessment, the purpose of product quality assessment, what the product is intended for, and the conditions of product use are usually taken into account [10]. Indicators of conformity of the product to its intended function play an important role in quality assessment, based on which criteria for optimizing product quality management are developed, which are often used to make the best management decisions [11]. Reliability indicators of a product, reliability is the property of performing specified tasks while maintaining the values of the indicators of the use of the product over a certain period. It follows from this definition that the reliability of the product is inextricably linked with its performance. The main indicators of reliability include uninterrupted operation, long-term durability, repairability, and maintainability [12]. The nomenclature of reliability indicators, the main methods of their calculation, and determination by experiments are regulated by relevant standards. The property of performing specified functions while maintaining its performance indicators within the specified limits during certain conditions and regimes of use of the item, the probability of non-destructive operation, the average service life before the first failure, operation until failure, the speed of failures, the guaranteed service life without damage are performance indicators [13]. Long-term durability indicators of the product description the service life until the first overhaul, modernization, and deregistration, taking into account its physical and mental wear and tear. The main indicators of long-term durability include resource, average service life, service life before the first overhaul, service life between repairs, service life until deregistration, and resource before the first overhaul [14].

Repairability is the property of a product that is adapted to prevent, detect, and eliminate product failures during maintenance and repair [15]. Indicators of serviceability for repair include the probability of recovery on time, average recovery time, average and relative labor of maintenance, average labor of repairs,

and indicators of average and relative costs of maintenance and repairs [16]. Durability is the property of maintaining the conditions of use of the product during the periods of storage and transportation specified in the technical documents and beyond. The indicators of shelf life consist of shelf life and average shelf life. In addition to the indicators considered above, concepts such as reliability, failure, workability, damage, and reproducibility are concepts that are integrally related to product reliability [17]. For most repairable types of products, the cost of replacement parts per unit of work performed by these types of products is one of the important indicators of operational reliability.

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